

DEVELOPMENT OF GRAPHENE COATED 3 PLY FABRIC FACE MASKS FOR SUPER PROTECTION

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Received: / Accepted: / Published online:
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Abstract *The emergence of a pandemic affecting the respiratory system can result in a significant demand for face masks. These include the use of cloth masks by large sections of the public, as can be seen during the current global spread of COVID-19. However, there is limited knowledge available on the performance of various commonly available fabrics used in cloth masks. Importantly, there is a need to evaluate filtration efficiencies as a function of aerosol particulate sizes in the 10 nm to 10 μm range, which is particularly relevant for respiratory virus transmission. We have carried out these studies for several common fabrics including, graphene, cotton, silk, chiffon, flannel, various synthetics, and their combinations. Although the filtration efficiencies for various fabrics when a single layer was used ranged from 5 to 80% and 5 to 95% for particle sizes of <300 nm and >300 nm (Chua et. al, 2020) respectively, the efficiencies improved when multiple layers were used and when using a specific combination of different fabrics. Filtration efficiencies of the hybrids (such as graphene-cotton-silk,) were >90% (for particles >300 nm). We speculate that the enhanced performance of the hybrids is likely due to the combined effect of aerosol layer, mechanical layer and electrostatic layer-based filtration. Graphene is a super-material that is nano sizes and produces a continuity graphene fabric layer. Nevertheless, the graphene layer may increase the temperature to 80°Celsius on the surface of the face mask when we leave it under sunlight for 20-30 minutes (Kaushik et. al, 2021). Cotton, the most widely used material for cloth masks performs better at higher weave densities and can make a significant difference in filtration efficiencies to prevent particles larger than a predetermined cut-off size from entering in either direction, whereas a layer of silk cloth was employed to absorb and trap users' body fluids. In general, we discover that combining various commercially available textiles in cloth masks can potentially provide significant protection against aerosol particle transmission.*

Keywords *Laboratory experiment· Deformable double-porosity soil· Vibration· Liquid migration· Image analysis method*

1 Introduction

Cloth face masks, surgical masks, and N95 masks are the most often used types of face masks. Figure 1a illustrates a Cloth mask example. Textile masks are simple to make at home using readily available cloth material. They are easily accessible and inexpensive. These masks are beneficial in preventing an infected person from transmitting their infections to another person or surrounding objects while conversing, sneezing, or coughing. However, it is ineffective at preventing the virus from reaching the wearer's nose or mouth. Even yet, wearing a fabric face mask is a significantly superior option to wearing no mask at all (Chua et al., 2020). Surgical masks, such as the one illustrated in Figure 1b, are also referred to as surgical masks. The mask wears by healthcare practitioners to prevent pathogens contained in liquid droplets and aerosols released from the surgeon's mouth or nose from entering the patient's open wound. These masks completely conceal the wearer's nose, mouth, and chin (Gaurav, Mittal, & Karn, 2020). Although these masks are superior to cloth masks, they are still significantly less effective in preventing infection because of the inability to filter microscopic particles and loose-fitting, which results in leakage from the sides. Its primary goal is to prevent the spread of big virus-infected droplets that come out of an infected wearer's lips when coughing or sneezing. N95 masks, as illustrated in Figure 1c, are round or oval and fit securely against the face to prevent air from escaping from the sides. Mask made of robust yet flexible non-woven polypropylene fibre. Worn the mask can eliminate 95% of contaminated particles larger than 3 microns. These masks have proven to be exceedingly infectious in terms of preventing infection in the wearer. Due to supply constraints and high demand during a pandemic, these masks recommended for healthcare personnel (Gaurav, Mittal, & Karn, 2020). However, this research will discuss the fabrication of a graphene-coated three-ply cloth reusable face mask and conductivity and temperature studies as depicted in Figure 2. We described a novel method for providing superior self-cleaning and photothermal features to currently available disposable non-woven face masks. We used a heat transfer approach to deposit few-layered graphene onto non-woven masks with a low melting point. On the treated masks' surfaces, aerosol phases observed, which may cause entering aqueous droplets to bounce off. The surface temperature of the functional mask may rapidly rise to over 80°C when exposed to sunshine, rendering the masks reusable following solar sterilization.

Figure 1a: Cloth Mask

Figure 1b: Surgical Mask

Figure 1c: N95 Mask

Figure 2: Graphene coated 3 ply face mask

2 Experimental Materials and Methods

2.1 The following materials were used to create these face masks:-

- i. Polyester fabric dimension 150mm x150mm
- ii. Cotton fabrics dimension 150mm x150mm
- iii. Silk fabric 150mm x150mm,
- iv. Graphene powder,
- v. Liquid type sanitizer
- vi. Cotton wool

2.2 Equipment's and tools:

- i. Rotating milling mixer brand Optimum
- ii. Hot press device brand Panasonic
- iii. Pencil
- iv. Baking paper
- v. Cardboard
- vi. Sewing machine

2.3 Preparation of compounds

15 gm graphene powder supplied by Zia Men in China combined with 15 grams of bio-adhesive. Both materials blended for 30 minutes at room temperature and humidity of 65 % using a rotating milling mixer set to 120 revolutions per minute (rpm). Then, using the hot press technique, the mixed solutions applied to the aerosol layer. After 24 hours at 50°C, the laminated aerosol film containing graphene solution dried. The conditioned aerosol layer (polyester fabric) is sewn together with two additional layers by mechanical (cotton fabric) and electrostatic (silk fabric) procedures as shown in Figure 3a, 3b and 3c. The complete graphene coated 3 ply face mask as shown in Figure 4a and 4b.

Figure 3a: Graphene compounding preparation

Figure 3b: Hot press technique

Figure 3c: Condition process

Figure 4a: Outer view

Figure 4b: Inner view

3 Results and Discussion

Additionally, a detailed experimental roadmap was created for the three-ply fabric film and hot-pressed graphene layers. At low temperatures, the actual momentum of the heat is converted to potential energy and employed to move graphene over the aerosol surface. The graphene layer affixed to the surface of the polyester layer adhered to it without harming it. Inspired by highlighting scientific findings that have been used to produce filters based on a variety of commercially accessible flexible substrates for filtering viruses, particulate matter, and air contaminants that can be simply integrated into graphene masks. A three-layered graphene mask is composed of fabric, with each layer serving a distinct purpose. This cost-effective graphene mask highlighted the augmentation of the CORONA virus (COVID-19) epidemic by studying the direction and exacerbation of the virus transmission passages globally throughout this pandemic, as seen in Figure 5. The reusable and sunlight sterilized multilayer graphene mask covering prevents both airborne transmission and direct communication by impeding the atomization and inhalation of virus-bearing aerosols. The outermost layer is waterproof and aids in the repellence of fluids such as mucosalalivary droplets [1391]. The filter in the middle prevents particles or germs larger than a specified size from penetrating in either direction. The innermost layer is composed of absorbent materials designed to collect mucosalalivary droplets from the user. Additionally, this layer absorbs moisture from exhaled air, enhancing comfort. Together, these three layers provide good protection for both the user and the surrounding community by restricting particle and pathogen penetration in both directions.

Figure 5: Passage of virus transmission

4 Conclusions

In general, a technique for augmenting dispersion few-layer graphene on a cost-effective advanced generation common cloth mask is envisioned, as conventional surgical masks with poor capacity are unable to eradicate germs trapped on the surface. As a result, almost 90% of bacteria continue to multiply after 810 hours (Gaurav et. al, 2020). Furthermore, these low-impact surgical masks may be unsuccessful at containing a global pandemic or even an epidemic in the event of an outbreak of a highly transmissible coronavirus and deadly disease. Simultaneously, the anti-COVID filtration properties of these UV-sterilised graphene multilayer masks are very application-dependent. Allowing for significant antibacterial coating performance that has already been established for CW-LIFF graphene, including protection against particulate matter, E. coli, and viruses. Meanwhile, more sophisticated procedures utilising super hydrophobic and photothermal techniques are expected to uncover derivatives suitable for usage in next-generation temperature-sensitizing chemicals.

Acknowledgements This study was supported by the Majlis Perbandaran Sepang (MPSepang), from the Setiausaha Kerajaan Negeri Selangor. The authors would also like to thank their respective institute.

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